

FACTORS INFLUENCING THE COLOR OF PROCESSED MEAT PRODUCTS: A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW

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Abstract: *Processed meat products play a significant role in the global food industry, offering consumers a diverse range of convenient and flavorful options. The color of processed meat is a crucial quality attribute that influences consumer perception, acceptability, and purchasing decisions. This research paper provides a comprehensive review of the factors affecting the color of processed meat products. It explores the impact of various factors such as animal species, muscle type, processing methods, additives, packaging, and storage conditions on the color characteristics of processed meats. Understanding these factors is essential for producers to optimize product quality, meet consumer expectations, and ensure market competitiveness.*

INTRODUCTION

Color is an important factor in processed meat products as it strongly influences consumer perception, selection, and acceptance [1]. Manufacturers are required to label processed meat products with information about additives and nutritional values [2]. The use of dyes in processed meat can affect specific food qualities, and their presence is influenced by factors such as water, flavorings, and high fat and carbohydrate contents [3]. Some dyes, such as carmine and annatto, can have allergic effects, while E150C and E150D caramels have potential carcinogenic effects [4]. Natural colorants from plant sources are being explored as alternatives to synthetic colorants, but there are limitations in incorporating them directly into plant-based meat products [5]. Plant polyphenols have been used as natural antioxidants to slow down the deterioration of red meat color due to oxidation. The color of meat is an important quality attribute, but there is a need for standardized color measuring systems and devices to ensure accurate and replicable results. Eliminating nitrite from cured meat products can affect color perception by consumers, but other sensory aspects and the "additive-free" claim can support the production of nitrite-free cured meats.

FACTORS AFFECTING PROCESSED MEAT COLOR

Meat color is influenced by species and breed variations. In poultry, the color lightness index of breast muscles differed significantly among hens, roosters, and capons, with capon meat being the lightest [1,6]. In sheep, packaging methods had a greater effect on meat color than breed and finishing feed, with vacuum skin packaging and modified atmosphere packaging affecting color parameters such as L*, a*, b*, hue, and chroma [7]. In pigs, a genome-wide association study revealed significant associations between single nucleotide polymorphisms and meat color traits, with several candidate genes identified as potential regulators of meat color [3,8]. Additionally, muscle myoglobin content was found to be positively correlated with favorable meat color and other quality traits such as marbling score and drip loss in pigs [9]. In cattle, heritability of meat absorbance spectra was greater for visible wavelengths, especially violet, blue, and green colors, compared to near-infrared wavelengths [7,10].

Differences in myoglobin content and distribution in different species can have an impact on meat color. Myoglobin is the main pigment responsible for the characteristic color of meat. In pigs, higher myoglobin content is associated with favorable meat color, higher marbling score, and less moisture content. In Iberian pigs, high myoglobin content is linked to a cherry-red color highly appreciated by consumers [11]. In beef, myoglobin exists in different forms and its interaction with oxygen affects the color. Discoloration starts from the interior and extends to the

surface, and the metmyoglobin layer can cause a loss of bright-red color. The addition of myoglobin to cell-based meat production can enhance tissue color, making it more similar to cooked beef [11,12].

The effect of species and muscle type on meat color was investigated in several studies. In one study, it was found that the interposition of pink muscle fibers in the dorsal ordinary muscle positively correlated with the breaking strength and hardness of raw fish meat [11]. Another study compared the meat tenderness and color attributes of different muscles from Boer Goat and Indigenous Veld Goat [13]. Additionally, a study on atypical dark-cutting beef found that differences in muscle pH and color were associated with lower glycolytic metabolites and glycogen degradation enzymes [7]. Furthermore, the impact of pulmonary arterial pressure on meat color was examined in Angus steers, and it was observed that high pulmonary arterial pressure resulted in lower color stability during retail display [7,11]. Finally, wet-aging time was found to affect the color of Korean native black goat meat, with longer aging periods leading to higher redness in the biceps femoris muscle [1,14].

Processing methods can have an effect on meat color. Different thermal and non-thermal processing techniques, such as sous-vide, microwave, stewing, roasting, boiling, frying, grilling, and steam cooking, can affect the color of meat [15]. High-pressure processing (HPP) applied to frozen and unfrozen minced meat samples can also influence meat color, with frozen and pressurized samples retaining their color for a longer period of time [3,16]. Additionally, the use of dyes in processed meat products can impact color, with certain dyes, such as carmine and annatto, having effects on color and potential allergic reactions [17]. Non-thermal processing technologies, such as high-pressure processing, pulsed electric field, ultrasonication, and irradiation, have been found to maintain better color attributes in processed food [5,18].

Nitrites and nitrates preserve and color processed meats by reacting with myoglobin. Salt extracts proteins, binds water, and stabilizes myoglobin for color retention. Phosphates improve moisture and texture, impacting pH and myoglobin stability. Spices like paprika add natural colors. Sugars enhance flavor and undergo browning reactions. Smoke imparts flavor and a brownish colour. Synthetic colorants may supplement color, but their use is regulated. These additives serve to preserve, flavor, and color processed meats, ensuring consistency and appeal while adhering to regulatory standards [19].

Packaging of processed meat affects color through oxygen and light exposure, additives, and material choice. Oxygen permeation in methods like vacuum or modified atmosphere packaging leads to browning and bacterial growth. Light exposure, especially fluorescent or natural, causes photo-oxidation and color changes [17]. Additives like antioxidants or nitrites preserve color and inhibit bacterial growth. Material opacity and oxygen barrier properties influence color maintenance. Effective temperature control also plays a role. Proper packaging techniques are vital to retain desired meat color and quality throughout its shelf life, ensuring freshness and consumer appeal [15,19].

The color of meat is influenced by storage conditions. Temperature control is vital, as both high and low temperatures can cause discoloration, such as browning or freezer burn. Oxygen exposure leads to oxidation, turning meat brown; thus, vacuum or modified atmosphere packaging is beneficial. Light exposure, especially UV light, can also prompt color changes, so light-blocking packaging is recommended [2,17]. Microbial growth can alter meat color, emphasizing the need for proper hygiene and storage practices. Additionally, as meat ages, its color may darken. Maintaining suitable storage conditions, minimizing oxygen and light exposure, and preventing microbial growth are crucial for preserving meat color [20].

CONCLUSION

The color of processed meat is a crucial factor influencing consumer perception and acceptance. Various factors such as animal species and breed, myoglobin content, muscle type, processing methods, additives, packaging, and storage conditions significantly impact meat color. Understanding these factors is essential for manufacturers to maintain consistency, quality, and safety standards in processed meat products. Additionally, the exploration of natural alternatives to synthetic colorants and the development of standardized color measuring systems are important avenues for further research. Ultimately, ensuring proper handling, processing, and packaging techniques are vital for preserving the desired color and overall quality of processed meats, meeting consumer expectations in an increasingly health-conscious market.

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